

Report on *in vitro* cardiac organoid model and preliminary perturbation data for doxorubicin

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Project summary:

The **S2TOX** - “*Mechanistic Assessment of Cardiotoxicity using Integrated In Silico and In Vitro Modeling*” project is an interdisciplinary initiative designed to replace traditional animal testing with a human-relevant, *in vitro-in silico* platform for evaluating drug-induced cardiotoxicity (DICT). Using anthracyclines as a primary case study, the project aims to mechanistically explain and predict how cardiac damage varies according to a patient’s sex and age.

S2TOX is structured into four Work Packages (WP):

- WP1 (*in silico* modeling): Optimizing an Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP) network and building a probabilistic Boolean model parameterized with human transcriptomics data.
- WP2 (*in vitro* testing): Establishing a human iPSC-derived cardiac organoid platform to generate functional and omics data for model calibration.
- WP3 (validation & trials): Validating the model against the organoid data and conducting virtual clinical trials to profile toxicity mechanisms across different patient profiles.
- WP4 (management & training): Open science dissemination, data management, and professional development.

iPSC Cardiac Organoid Protocol

This protocol describes the generation of 3D cardiac organoids from human induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSC) using AggreWell™800 for controlled aggregation, followed by cardiac differentiation and early maturation. It standardizes (i) single-cell iPSC preparation with ROCK inhibition, (ii) microwell seeding at 10,000 cells/miniwell (3.0×10^6 /well), (iii) 24-h aggregation, (iv) two-day recovery without ROCKi, and (v) a 7-day differentiation + 7-day early maturation with 48-h medium changes. The workflow is tuned for high viability, and reproducible onset of beating (~Day 7).

The plate conditioning, aggregation logic, and quality control checkpoints adapt general microwell spheroid principles described in Miura et al. (2022) to cardiac tissue and AggreWell™800; step timings, centrifugation speeds, hypoxia (5% O₂), and media handling reflect in-house practice from Sampaolesi Lab (KU Leuven) for cardiac organoid specification and survival (Duellen et al., 2022; Marini et al., 2022; Vervliet et al., 2023).

1) Preparation (before dissociation)

1. Warm E8, E8+Revitacel, Accutase to room temperature (RT).
2. Prepare support medium: E8 + ROCKi (Revitacel (Gibco) 1:100) 10 μM.
 - *Why*: Increases post-dissociation survival.
3. Check incubators: 37 °C, 5% CO₂; hypoxia available (5% O₂) for differentiation.
4. Plan cell numbers: 10,000 cells/miniwell × 300 miniwells = 3.0×10^6 cells/well.
 - *Tip*: Prepare ~10% extra cells.

2) Condition [AggreWell™800 plate](#)

5. Add 500 μL anti-adherence rinsing solution (AARS)/well, 5 min RT.
 - *Why*: Prevents cell sticking to plastic; promotes uniform aggregation.
6. If bubbles, but they will be there, so: 1,300 g, 5 min spin; aspirate AARS.
 - *Why*: Bubbles block microwells leading uneven spheroids.
7. Wash with 1 mL PBS; aspirate.
8. Add 0.5 mL E8 + ROCKi per well.
9. Hold plate in 37 °C incubator until seeding.

3) Dissociate iPSC to single cells

11. Aspirate culture medium; wash 1× PBS.
12. Add Accutase (6 well plates; 0.5 - 1 mL).
 - *Why*: Accutase allows the dissociation of hiPSC colonies into single cells.
13. Incubate at 37 °C, 7–10 min until detachment; avoid over-incubation.
14. Gently up and down 2–3× with a serological pipette to assist the disaggregation of the colonies into single cells.
15. Transfer to a 15-mL Falcon tube.
16. Rinse the plate with DF12 (~6 mL); pool to ~10 mL total.

4) Pellet, resuspend, count, calculate

17. Centrifuge at 200 g, 4 min and aspirate supernatant.
18. Resuspend in E8 + ROCKi (10 μM).
19. Count viable cells (dye with Trypan Blue) on Countess II; note viability %.
20. Adjust to 3.0×10^6 live cells/mL.
21. Prepare 1.0 mL/well of this suspension. Final volume is 1.5 mL/well.

5) Seed into AggreWell (Day -3)

22. Add 1.0 mL cell suspension to each conditioned well (1.5 mL of final volume).
23. Gently pipette to evenly distribute.
24. Centrifuge at 100 g, 3 min plate spin.
25. Check in the microscope: even distribution, no bubbles, no overfilled microwells.
 - *Why*: Catch issues now; reseed if bad.
26. Incubate for 24 h, 37 °C, 5% CO₂ and 5% O₂.

6) Post-aggregation recovery (remove ROCKi - Day -2 and -1)

27. At ~24 h, let spheroids settle 5–10 min.
28. Full medium change: remove all the medium, and add 1.5 mL E8 (no ROCKi) gently.
29. Next day: partial change, remove 1 mL of medium and add 1.0 mL E8 (no ROCKi).

7) Cardiac differentiation and maturation (Days 0 to 14)

30. Medium change as follows:
 - On day 0, Cardiomyocyte differentiation medium A.
 - On day 2, Cardiomyocyte differentiation medium B.
 - From day 4 onwards, maintenance medium

(<https://www.thermofisher.com/order/catalog/product/A2921201>).
31. Expect beating ~Day 7 (±).
32. Keep 48 h media changes.

8) Harvest / downstream

33. Let spheroids settle; remove medium carefully.
34. Collect with wide-bore tips for assays/fixation.

Abbreviations

- iPSC: induced pluripotent stem cell
- AggW800: AggreWell™ 800, 24-well plate (STEMCELL #34811)
- AARS: Anti-Adherence Rinsing Solution
- E8: Essential 8 (or E8 Flex) medium
- ROCKi: ROCK inhibitor Y-27632 (10 µM final)
- DF12: DMEM/F-12
- RT: room temp
- QC: quality control

Exposure assay

Organoids were maintained under standard conditions (37 °C, 5% CO₂, humidified incubator) in a model-appropriate maintenance medium. Doxorubicin (DOX) working solutions were prepared fresh in vehicle (Milli-Q water). Organoids were allocated to three groups: Control (0.1% DMSO), 0.5 µM DOX, and 2.0 µM DOX. DOX was added gently to minimize disturbance, and cultures were incubated for 24 h. After 24 h, wells were washed once with prewarmed (37 °C) maintenance medium to remove residual compounds and immediately subjected to the methods described below.

Morphological assessment

Methods

Qualitative Morphology Assessment

Organoids were imaged on an inverted Leica DMI1 microscope using Köhler illumination and a 5× objective with constant exposure, gain, and white balance across conditions and using the LAS ez v3.4.0 software. For each well, non-overlapping fields spanning the central two-thirds of the well were acquired to avoid edge artifacts and repeated sampling. We reviewed all fields on calibrated displays using identical brightness/contrast settings. Morphology was assessed qualitatively, describing shape, edge quality, surface compaction, internal texture, presence of satellite bodies and budding, and relative size.

Quantitative Morphology Assessment

Quantitative morphometric analysis was performed on bright-field images acquired with the same condition as described previously. Image processing and feature extraction were conducted in R version 4.4.0 (2024-04-24 ucrt) (Posit team, 2024) and R Studio version 2023.12.1.402 (Ocean Storm) (R Core Team, 2024) using the EBImage package (Pau et al., 2010) and sf package (Pebesma, 2018) for robust geometric calculations. Consistent with label-free approaches for organoid characterization (Serafini et al., 2024), each image was converted to greyscale and denoised with a Gaussian filter ($\sigma = 1.0$), and inverted to render organoids bright on a dark background. Segmentation was performed using Otsu global thresholding followed by morphological opening and hole filling to generate binary masks, a widely adopted method for initial organoid binarization in brightfield images (Gritti et al., 2021). Touching organoids were separated using a watershed algorithm seeded by local maxima of the Euclidean distance map. To ensure analysis of relevant biological structures, objects smaller than 500 pixels were filtered out as noise, and objects contacting the image border were excluded. For each labelled object, we extracted projected area, aspect ratio (major axis/minor axis), and radius ratio (maximum radius/minimum radius) to characterize the non-spherical morphology. Solidity was calculated as the ratio of the object area to the area of its convex hull, with the hull area computed via polygon masking to ensure geometric validity. All measurements were recorded in pixel units and converted to µm using a scaling factor of 1.9216 µm/pixel.

Statistical analysis

All per-object morphometric data were aggregated by experimental group prior to analysis. Statistical computations were performed in R using the *rstatix* (Kassambara, 2023) and *multcompView* (Spencer Graves et al., 2024) packages. For each metric (Projected Area, Aspect Ratio, Radius Ratio, Solidity), we computed descriptive summaries (n, mean, SD) per group. To ensure analysis of relevant biological structures, segmentation artifacts were excluded via a size filter (area < 500 pixels) prior to statistical testing. Given the non-normal distribution of the morphometric data (confirmed via Shapiro-Wilk testing) and unequal variance across groups, non-parametric methods were employed for all inferential tests. Global differences between groups were assessed using the Kruskal-Wallis rank-sum test. Post hoc pairwise comparisons were conducted using Dunn's test with Bonferroni correction for multiple testing to control the family-wise error rate ($\alpha = 0.05$). Pairwise adjusted p-values were summarized as compact letter displays (lowercase a, b, c); groups sharing a letter were not significantly different for that metric after adjustment.

Results

Qualitative Morphology Assessment

Control (untreated): Organoids across fields remained compact and morphologically uniform, with smooth perimeters. Structures are predominantly ovoid or kidney-shaped, with limited elongation and presence of spherical ones. Internal texture was homogeneous and dense, with no evidence of cavitation. Size variability was moderate, and satellite formations were present, although infrequent. Collectively, this condition reflects a cohesive population of healthy organoids.

0.5 μM DOX: Numerous organoids showed axial elongation, lobation, or constricted “dumbbell-like” morphologies. Peripheral budding events were observed. While margins remain mostly intact, contour undulations were common, and inter-organoid fusions seem to occur, yielding irregular, compound structures. Despite these changes, core regions remain dense and non-cavitated.

2.0 μM DOX: The fields were dominated by a mixed population of small, rounded micro-aggregates and a minority of large, amorphous bodies. Boundaries were frequently irregular or fragmented, possibly due to re-aggregation following fragmentation. Size distribution was broad, and proximity among organoids was markedly reduced, possibly promoting aggregation into larger irregular clusters. Several bodies displayed internal mottling or peripheral translucency, indicative of decreased density.

There seems to be a dose-responsive disruption of organoid architecture. At baseline, the population was compact and cohesive. Exposure to 0.5 μM induced anisotropic deformation and lobation without cavitation. At 2.0 μM , fragmentation dominated, yielding numerous small spheroids and irregular masses with variable compaction.

Figure 1. Representative micrographs illustrating dose-dependent architectural changes in organoid morphology. (A) Control cultures exhibit compact structures with smooth, well-defined borders and uniform internal density. (B) At 0.5 μM DOX, organoids display increased morphological heterogeneity, including elongation, lobation, and frequent necking; partial fusions and peripheral budding are evident. (C) Exposure to 2.0 μM DOX results in extensive fragmentation and re-aggregation into irregular clusters of micro- and macro-aggregates. Magnification = 10x.

Quantitative Morphology Assessment

Across conditions, quantitative analysis revealed selective shifts in organoid size and geometry. In contrast to solidity, which remained stable across all groups, both projected area and aspect ratio varied significantly after multiple-comparison adjustment. Specifically, the 0.5 μM treatment group exhibited increased projected area compared to controls, while aspect ratio measurements indicated a significant shift in elongation. Furthermore, the radius ratio, quantifying the depth of shape indentations, differed significantly between groups. Taken together, these data indicate that doxorubicin modulates organoid size and shape complexity. Table 1 summarizes the quantitative results.

Table 1. Morphometric summary (mean \pm SD) of cardiac organoids across Control, 0.5 μM , and 2.0 μM doxorubicin; values are in μm unless noted, and bracketed letters denote groups that differ significantly.

	Control	0.5 μM	2.0 μM
Area (μm^2)	35170.52 \pm 54759.50 [a]	48712.12 \pm 66218.88 [b]	38857.06 \pm 52375.14 [ab]
Aspect ratio (major/minor)	2.39 \pm 2.16 [a]	2.28 \pm 2.56 [b]	2.36 \pm 3.67 [ab]
Radius Ratio (max/min)	33.23 \pm 71.06 [a]	33.51 \pm 124.93 [ab]	29.30 \pm 76.22 [b]
Radius CV	0.38 \pm 0.13 [a]	0.35 \pm 0.13 [ab]	0.34 \pm 0.14 [b]
Solidity (area/convex area)	0.58 \pm 0.40 [a]	0.59 \pm 0.36 [a]	0.59 \pm 0.38 [a]

Cardiac organoid beating rate

Methods

Bright-field video recordings were analyzed using R version 4.4.0 (2024-04-24 ucrt) (Posit team, 2024) and R Studio version 2023.12.1.402 (Ocean Storm) (R Core Team, 2024), with a custom automated pipeline adopting a pixel-based motion vector approach similar to methods previously established for cardiac organoid characterization (Devarasetty et al., 2017).

Video preprocessing and segmentation

Video frames were extracted using the `av` package (Ooms, 2023). To address encoding inconsistencies common in microscopy video formats (e.g., non-interleaved data), a robust extraction routine was implemented that defaulted to native decoding if standard frame-rate enforcement failed. All videos were temporally standardized to 30 frames per second (fps) and spatially down-sampled by a factor of 0.5 to improve signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) and computational efficiency.

Background estimation was performed by computing the pixelwise temporal median of 80 frames uniformly spaced across the recording. This background model was subtracted from individual frames to highlight contractile motion. Organoids were segmented using the `imager` package (Barthelme, 2020) via Gaussian blurring followed by automated thresholding using Otsu's method. Morphological operations (closing and opening) were applied to reduce noise. Connected components were labelled, and regions of interest (ROIs) were defined by filtering components based on area (3000 - 10000000 pixels) to exclude debris and aggregates.

Motion Quantification and Beat Detection

For each ROI, a one-dimensional motion trace was generated by calculating the frame-to-frame absolute difference in pixel intensity, averaged across the ROI, serving as a surrogate for contractile force and frequency (Devarasetty et al., 2017; Joddar et al., 2022). A running-median baseline (window size = 1 s) was subtracted to correct for illumination drift.

Beat rate was estimated as follows: the primary estimate was derived from the autocorrelation function of the detrended trace, identifying peaks corresponding to physiological rates (30–240 beats per minute, bpm). A secondary spectral estimate was obtained via Fast Fourier Transform after applying a Hann window. The spectral signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) was calculated as the ratio of peak power to median power within the physiological rates. An ROI was classified as "beating" only if the estimated rate fell within the physiological range and the spectral SNR was ≥ 10 .

Statistical analysis

Statistical analyses were performed using the `rstatix` (Kassambara, 2023) and the native `stats` packages. Data distributions were assessed for normality; as assumptions for parametric tests were not met, nonparametric methods were employed. Beating Efficiency: The proportion of beating versus non-beating organoids was compared across groups using Fisher's Exact Test. Pairwise comparisons were conducted using Fisher's Exact Test with Bonferroni correction for multiple comparisons. Beat Rate (BPM): Differences in beat rate among the beating sub-population were evaluated using the

Kruskal–Wallis rank-sum test. Post-hoc pairwise comparisons were performed using Dunn’s test (Dunn, 1964) with Bonferroni correction. All tests were two-sided, and a p -value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant. Data are presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) or percentage (count/total) as appropriate.

Results

Doxorubicin treatment significantly reduced the spontaneous beating rate of treated cardiac organoids in a dose-dependent manner (Figure 2 A). While the global analysis indicated a significant variance in the proportion of beating organoids ($p = 0.02$, Figure 2 B), pairwise comparisons showed only a statistically non-significant, however biologically important, trend towards reduced beating efficiency in the high-dose group (68.9% vs 50.5%, $p = 0.07$).

Figure 2. Quantitative and representative analysis of beating activity in cardiac organoids under different treatments. (A) Violin plots of beating rates (BPM) for cardiac organoids by treatment group (Control, 0.5 μ M, 2.0 μ M); violins show the full distribution, with embedded boxplots

(median and interquartile range) and individual points. * denotes $p < 0.05$. **(B)** Percentage of beating and non-beating organoids. **(C)** Representative motion trace from a beating organoid, with the detrended signal over time and detected beats marked as thick blue lines. **(D)** Representative motion trace from a non-beating organoid, illustrating the absence of stable periodicity and lack of consistent beat detections.

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